

DEVELOPING CULTURAL COMPETENCE OF FUTURE KOREAN LANGUAGE TEACHERS

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Abstract. *As Uzbekistan focuses more on learning foreign languages, including Korean, international cooperation in education is becoming an important task. Using Korean educational experience in the national curriculum will contribute to a number of areas by developing the cultural competencies of future Korean language teachers.*

Keywords: *Foreign languages, National Curriculum, method, methodology, educational methods, Korean educational experience, cultural competencies.*

РАЗВИТИЕ КУЛЬТУРНОЙ КОМПЕТЕНТНОСТИ БУДУЩИХ УЧИТЕЛЕЙ КОРЕЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА

Аннотация. *Поскольку Узбекистан уделяет больше внимания изучению иностранных языков, включая корейский, международное сотрудничество в сфере образования становится важной задачей. Использование корейского образовательного опыта в национальной учебной программе будет способствовать ряду направлений путем развития культурных компетенций будущих учителей корейского языка.*

Ключевые слова: *Иностранные языки, Национальная учебная программа, метод, методология, образовательные методы, корейский образовательный опыт, культурные компетенции.*

Educational and cultural ties between Uzbekistan and the Republic of Korea have been strengthened in recent years, opening up new opportunities and avenues for cooperation. These ties are developing through exchanges of professors, teachers, students, research centers, and cultural exchanges between the two countries. While the Korean education system is known for its innovative approaches, high-quality education, and the use of advanced technologies, the Uzbek education system is notable for its rich historical traditions, cultural values, and modern changes..

Many cultural exchange programs are being implemented between Uzbekistan and Korea to study Korean culture. Within the framework of these programs, teachers and cultural experts from Korea come to Uzbekistan and give lectures on the Korean language, literature, art, and traditions. Uzbek students have the opportunity to study or exchange work experience in Korea.

Obtaining new information about advanced practices and innovations in the science and education systems of Uzbekistan and Korea. Currently, the main task of teaching foreign languages is to train future specialists who can speak one of the foreign languages fluently, understand without translators, hear and read the news of world science and technology in the original language, and contribute to strengthening the cultural, economic, and friendly ties of our country with other countries. In order to implement the national policy on personnel training being implemented in our republic, an Institute of Foreign Languages was established in 1994 in Samarkand to train personnel capable of teaching foreign languages and establishing relations in foreign languages..

Korean culture — is a rich culture that encompasses its own values, customs, arts, history, and social systems. Korean culture has been shaped over the centuries by its traditional values and modern developments, and has had a significant international influence.

Korean language — It is an integral part of culture and reflects the social system in Korean society. The unique features of the language, including formal and informal forms, a system of honorifics, and traditional expressions, reflect the deep scope of Korean culture.

In recent years, our republic has been working to further improve the education system, continue the policy of training highly qualified personnel in line with the modern needs of the labor market, introduce international standards for assessing the quality of education and training, improve the quality and efficiency of higher education institutions, effectively use innovative forms and methods of education, the latest pedagogical and information and communication technologies, distance and software, didactic materials, and create a normative framework for education. “Automation of education management using modern information and communication technologies in the educational process, creation of a single electronic platform for distance learning using modern educational technologies and new mechanisms for assessing the qualifications of employees and its application in all areas of education, introduction of highly effective international practice in the education system aimed at organizing training in the field of innovative activities” have been set as priority tasks[1].

Also, today there are several different methods of innovative educational technologies.

Also, increasing the effectiveness of teaching and learning foreign languages through modern technologies is the most important issue. The introduction of modern communication technologies in the educational process, their purposeful, correct and productive use, through which it is necessary to increase the student's interest in a foreign language, as well as the use of

graphic organizers in teaching a foreign language to explain new words and grammatical rules related to the subject, is in line with the goal. In the programs of the subject "Korean language", it is necessary to improve the oral and written speech of students in Korean, equip them with the necessary knowledge on language levels, and use this knowledge and skills appropriately.

Modern methods of teaching Korean have improved over the past two decades. Nowadays, it is appropriate to use modern methods and techniques in teaching Korean. In fact, there are many different strategies for teaching foreign languages to language learners. Nowadays, the process of learning Korean involves more student-centered lessons, which takes time. Therefore, we need to use modern methods in teaching a foreign language. Modern teaching methods mainly help to form or develop an effective understanding of science and technology.

In higher education institutions, the method of remote listening is used in lessons on the development and improvement of listening skills in Korean. In this case, students learn to listen to and perceive speech in Korean. As N.D. Galskova noted, up to 60% of the paralinguistic elements of speech are conveyed by information in audio messages. Audiovisual materials not only allow us to hear, but also significantly facilitate the perception of information by observing the acoustic elements of speech through intonation, raising and lowering of sounds, pauses, etc., as well as gestures, facial expressions. At the same time, a situation of indirect immersion in the language environment occurs, which contributes to the more successful development of oral communication skills and the removal of the language barrier¹.

Teaching Korean - It is not just a process of teaching a language, but also involves providing students with a deep cultural exchange by teaching them Korean culture, traditions, history, and literature. The Korean language requires not only the mastery of grammatical and lexical rules, but also the development of important skills in pronunciation, writing, and cultural perspectives.

When talking about effective methods for teaching Korean, there are several main approaches to consider:

1. Main directions of Korean language teaching methodology:
 - a) Grammar-Translation Method;
 - b) Communicative Approach;
 - c) Culture-Based Approach;

¹ M.Mashkurova Koreys tilini o'qitish metodikasi *Международный научный журнал № 15(100), часть 2 «Новости образования: исследование в XXI веке»* Ноября, 2023.

2. Methods and technologies used in teaching Korean: :

- a) Teaching using multimedia and technology;
- b) Interactive methods in teaching;
- c) Teaching pronunciation and intonation.

3. Developing cultural competence in teaching Korean:

a) Studying Korean traditions and holidays – providing information about important Korean holidays such as Seollal (New Year) and Chuseok (Pentecost), and explaining to students the cultural and historical significance of these holidays.

b) Korean Literature and Art – Teaching Korean literature, poetry, and drama genres helps students gain a deeper understanding of Korea's cultural heritage.

c) Cultural exchanges – inviting teachers from Korea to study Korean culture, creating opportunities to study or do internships in Korea.

4. Tips for Success in Learning Korean

a) Practical application of the language – When learning Korean, one should not limit oneself to books or grammar rules. It is necessary to create opportunities for students to use the language in real life. Madaniyatni chuqur o'rganish – Tilni o'rganishda madaniy kontekstni hisobga olish, tilning so'zlashuvdagi muhim jihatlari (hurmat ko'rsatish, so'zlarning ijtimoiy konteksti) e'tibor qaratish kerak.

b) Simplify the structure – Korean grammar and pronunciation can sometimes be complex. Teachers need to teach the language systematically using simple and clear examples, exercises, and practices.

Teaching Korean is a comprehensive process that not only teaches the language, but also develops cultural understanding. Enriching teaching methodologies with modern technologies, communicative approaches, and culture-based teaching increases the effectiveness of teaching Korean. By learning Korean, students not only master the language but also Korean culture, gaining the opportunity to develop better understanding and communication between the two cultures.

In this article, we will examine methodologies and practical methods aimed at developing the cultural competence of Korean language teachers.

The importance of cultural competence - cultural competence in language teaching is not only about learning grammar or vocabulary, but also about understanding the social, historical, cultural, and ethnic aspects of the language being studied.

When teaching Korean, students need to understand not only the language, but also the customs, values, historical events, and culture of the Korean people. This introduces young people to a sense of respect and empathy for other cultures, and also facilitates the use of language in context.

Methodology for developing cultural competence - it is necessary to use various methods and techniques to develop cultural competence. The following methodological approaches will be effective in providing future Korean language teachers with cultural competence.

- use of cultural materials;
- analysis of situations from a cultural perspective;
- interactive teaching methods;
- development of intercultural dialogue;
- meetings with representatives of the local Korean language and culture.

The relationship between cultural competence and language learning - It is important to consider the role of cultural competence in teaching Korean. Cultural knowledge helps to fully understand the specifics of the language, such as formal and informal speech in Korean, expressions that express cultural values, customs, and values. Students equipped with cultural competence will have an easier time expressing their thoughts clearly and logically in Korean.

Korean culture is distinguished by its rich history, values, arts, and traditions. Respect for the lifestyle, approach to life, and values of the Korean people plays an important role in establishing contacts with other cultures and developing mutual understanding. Korean culture is growing in influence not only in the Asian region but also around the world.

The development of cultural competence of Korean language teachers is aimed at ensuring their deep understanding not only of the language, but also of Korean culture. Cultural competence plays an important role in helping teachers establish effective communication with Uzbek students and pupils, and in introducing Korean culture, traditions, and society. This competence allows teachers to enrich their pedagogical approaches, methodologies, and cultural knowledge. By updating their cultural and linguistic knowledge, Korean language teachers are able to provide students with deeper and more effective education. As a result, the development of cultural competence is important not only for teachers, but also for the development of intercultural relations.

REFERENCES

1. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2019-yil 8-oktabrdagi PF-5847-sonli farmoni «O‘zbekiston Respublikasi oliy ta’lim tizimini 2030 yilgacha rivojlantirish konsepsiyasini tasdiqlash to‘g‘risida».
2. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. Erkin va farovon, demokratik O‘zbekiston davlatini birgalikda barpo etamiz. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti lavozimiga kirishish tantanali marosimiga bag‘ishlangan Oliy Majlis palatalarining qo‘shma majlisidagi nutq. – T.: O‘zbekiston, 2017. - 56 b.
3. M.Mashkurova Koreys tilini o‘qitish metodikasi *Международный научный журнал № 15(100), часть 2 «Новости образования: исследование в XXI веке»* Ноябрь , 2023.
4. <https://oefen.uz/uz/documents/diplom-ishlar/umumiy/koreys-tili-darslarida-leksik-kompetensiyani-rivojlantirish-metodlari>
5. WWW.ziyonet.uz
6. WWW.tdpu.uz
7. WWW.edu.uz